

STUDY OF THE ELECTROSPARK DISPERSION PROCESS OF MATERIALS TO OBTAIN NANO-SIZED COMPONENTS OF PROMISING POWDER COMPOSITIONS FOR ADDITIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: A laboratory electric spark machine was developed, that makes it possible to create an overvoltage at the inter-electrode gap between the dispersible electrodes. The possibility of obtaining nanopowders of conductive materials by the method of electrospark erosion under the conditions of a significant overvoltage of the discharge gap is shown. The prospects of obtaining powder materials in low tonnage volumes for additive technologies with high economic effectiveness are shown.

Keywords: nanoparticles, nanopowders, additive technologies, powder compositions, electrospark dispersion.

Введение

At the beginning of the 21st century, the low material utilization rate became a significant problem in high-tech industries: as a result of processing blanks, up to 70-80% of purchased material becomes industrial waste. This problem began to be solved by introducing advanced production technologies. Currently, the most effective concept is recognized as the so-called additive technologies, which imply not the processing of a workpiece to obtain the desired shape, but the formation of parts of the desired shape from raw materials, of which exactly as much is required as the part contains. Nowadays, the emergence of additive technologies in high-tech industry looks quite realistic. This is primarily due to the development of laser technology, which has made it possible to create a relatively inexpensive technology for obtaining parts by layer-by-layer laser sintering from powder materials. At the same time, it became clear that such additive technologies are economically feasible to use in the production of small batches of products with high added value, i.e. the introduction of additive technologies is the next step to increasing competitiveness for rocket, engine, aircraft, shipbuilding, as well as for energy, transport and agricultural engineering. Manufacturers who are unable to switch to new technologies will be forced to leave the market.

However, the introduction of additive technologies in high-tech industry requires a huge range of powders of various metals and alloys, but in relatively small quantities due to the low serial production of high-tech products, therefore, universal technologies for the production of metal and alloy powders that allow working with any materials and obtaining powders of various fractions in low-tonnage volumes are of greatest interest to industry. It

should be noted that the technologies for the production of powders for additive technologies must also have good economic indicators, since the cost of these powders is currently too high for their mass use [1].

Along with increasing the economic efficiency of powder production for additive technologies, work is underway to improve their compositions and formulations to obtain higher quality products. Literally over the past year, interest has arisen in using nanopowders of metals and other materials for these purposes. It is proposed to mix nanopowders with micron-sized particles to increase accuracy, reduce roughness and improve the service characteristics of parts obtained by layer-by-layer laser or electron-beam sintering. For example, work in this area has started in the format of a public-private partnership through the Russian Academy of Sciences at the Institute of Strength Physics and Materials Science SB RAS [2]. However, there is a significant obstacle to the implementation of additive technologies in the Russian Federation, which is caused by a partial ban on the supply of equipment for the production of micro- and nanopowders to our country. Not only industrial enterprises of the military-industrial complex, but even research organizations, such as VIAM [3], have encountered such a restriction.

There are two main methods for obtaining metal and alloy nanopowders - chemical and physical (dispersion) [4-6]. When producing specific nanopowders in large volumes, the chemical method usually has an advantage. When producing a wide range of nanopowders in small-tonnage volumes, it is advisable to use physical methods, among which the most promising are considered to be: electric explosion of wire; vacuum-arc dispersion; laser ablation; electrical erosion dispersion of materials.

In order to obtain submicron and nanosized powders of conductive magnetic materials for magnetic recording devices, scientists from the University of California, under the leadership of Professor Berchowitz, proposed a very simple and accessible method of their synthesis based on the electric spark erosion of the initial materials in a liquid dielectric [7]. In fact, their work used the well-known method of electric spark processing of materials, but implemented according to a different scheme, aimed at intensive destruction of the materials of the working electrodes in order to obtain powders of these materials. However, this method, in the case of obtaining nanometer-sized powders, like most other known high-performance methods for obtaining nanopowders, has a drawback consisting in a large spread of sizes of nanoparticles obtained in a single process, which can range from units to hundreds of nanometers, which significantly complicates the production or isolation of fractions of nanoparticles with the required characteristics for the preparation of powder compositions for additive technologies.

Further studies aimed at studying the processes of electrospark synthesis of nanopowders confirmed the possibility of obtaining nanopowders of various conductive materials, including alloys of complex composition [8, 9]. Studies were conducted on the influence of the dielectric liquid media used on the process of synthesis of nanopowders, both traditional for electrospark processing of materials (for example, kerosene), and other organic and inorganic liquids, including cryogenic ones [10, 11]. At present, the results of the research obtained by various groups have allowed us to better understand the process of electrospark synthesis of nanoparticles, but have not eliminated the disadvantage of this method for obtaining nanopowders, associated with a large spread in the sizes of nanoparticles. In our opinion, this may be caused by several factors at once. In [10], it is proposed to use discharge pulses with an energy of less than 100 mJ for the synthesis of nanopowders, which is difficult when using standard pulse generators for electrospark installations, which, as a rule, were used by researchers when conducting experiments. In addition, mathematical modeling of the behavior of vapor-gas bubbles formed during breakdown in a liquid dielectric, carried out in work [12], showed that their collapse in a number of cases is

accompanied by division into several parts, the sizes of which depend on the conditions of their formation, which leads to the appearance of several nanoparticles of different sizes.

Methods

Based on the study of already known results, the authors made the assumption that it is possible to reduce the spread of particle sizes of nanopowders by changing the conditions of spark breakdown so that the breakdown occurs faster and is localized on a smaller area of the electrodes. This can apparently be achieved if a significant overvoltage is created on the electrodes subjected to electric spark dispersion, which is impossible in any of the previously described schemes. To create an overvoltage on the electrodes, another switching element must be added to the circuit, which would switch the capacitor charged to a high voltage with the electrodes at a voltage on the capacitor significantly greater than the breakdown voltage between these electrodes for the dielectric liquid medium used.

To conduct the experiment, an experimental electrospark laboratory setup was developed that allows creating overvoltage on dispersible electrodes, the functional diagram of which is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Uncontrolled air spark gap (a), dispersible silver electrodes (b), general view of a laboratory electric spark installation (c)

In the laboratory setup, a high-voltage capacitor (C) with a capacity of 1000 pF was used during the experiments. The capacitor was charged from a high-voltage AC transformer with a frequency of 50 Hz to a voltage in the range from 1 to 10 kV. An uncontrolled air gap FV1 was used to switch the high-voltage capacitor. This gap was 1 mm wide between two electrodes with an area of 50 mm². A photograph of the uncontrolled air gap used in the laboratory setup is shown in Fig. 2, a. The capacitor charging rate in the laboratory setup circuit was set by the resistance R of the charging circuit.

Distilled water was used as a liquid dielectric to fill the interelectrode gap formed between two dispersible FV2 electrodes in the experiments. The electrodes of the laboratory setup were made of silver (Fig. 2, b). During the experiments, a gap of 70 μm was set between the electrodes. To ensure uniform consumption of the electrodes during the spark erosion process, the surfaces of the working electrodes were rotated relative to each other. The general appearance of the laboratory setup with an uncontrolled air gap, electrodes, and a rotation drive system is shown in Fig. 2, c.

Results and Discussions

During the experiments, the capacitor, charged to a high voltage sufficient for the simultaneous breakdown of the air gap and the interelectrode gap, was discharged through

the air gap onto the working electrodes immersed in a 1-liter bath of distilled water. For the established parameter values of the laboratory electric spark setup, the breakdown voltage was about 4 kV, while the discharge current in the pulse was from 1 to 2 kA. Electric spark dispersion of the electrodes was carried out for 10 min.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the distribution of the obtained silver nanopowder particles by size

Fig. 3. Typical TEM images of the obtained silver nanopowder particles

The silver nanopowder samples obtained in the experiments were subjected to a particle size distribution study using the dynamic light scattering (DLS) method. The measurement was performed using a Photocor Compact-Z device. The particle size distribution diagram of the obtained silver nanopowders (Fig. 3) showed that this distribution is quite narrow, with more than 80% of the nanoparticles having a diameter of 20 to 45 nm. In addition to the DLS method, images obtained on a LEO-912 AB OMEGA transmission electron microscope (TEM) were used to measure the particle size distribution of the nanopowders. Typical TEM images of the particles are shown in Fig. 4. It is evident that most of the particles are spherical, and their sizes are 20+40 nm, which confirms the results of the DLS study.

To assess the composition of the obtained silver nanopowders, their electronogram was made, which was used for comparison with the electronogram of a sample of crystalline silver. The comparison showed that the obtained nanopowder particles consist of crystalline silver without noticeable admixture of oxides or salts. The electronograms of the particles of the obtained silver nanopowder and the sample of crystalline silver are shown in Fig. 4, a and b, respectively.

Fig. 4. Electron diffraction patterns of silver nanopowder particles (a) and a sample of crystalline silver (b)

The studies have shown the possibility of obtaining nano-rocks of conductive materials with a small spread of particle sizes by the method of electric spark erosion under conditions of significant overvoltage of the discharge gap. The obtained particles of silver nanopowders had a spherical shape and a fairly narrow size distribution. Apparently, the process under study is promising for creating on its basis a technology for obtaining powder materials from metals and alloys for additive technologies and equipment for their production in small-tonnage volumes. The economic efficiency of such technology can be indirectly estimated through the productivity of the machines for electrical discharge cutting of materials. Thus, for the LS ZNC series machines of LIEN SHENG Mechanical & Electrical Co., Ltd. with a power consumption of 10 kW•h, the maximum amount of dispersed material is 42,000 mm³/h or 42 cm³/h under the condition of using a dielectric liquid in a closed cycle.

To better study the process of obtaining nanopowders and understand the influence of discharge gap overvoltage on this process, further research is necessary for different ratios of discharge gaps and different conductive materials.

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